

Working Paper

The European Stability Mechanism

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Abstract: This chapter analyses the role of the European Stability Mechanism (ESM) during and after the COVID-19 crisis as well as shortly in relation to funding the war in Ukraine. In specific, the chapter discusses the Pandemic Crisis Support Facility, an assistance instrument adopted within the ESM that was never used. The new facility is analysed especially in light of the no bail-out clause of Article 125 TFEU. Furthermore, the failed attempt to amend the ESM Treaty, which would have made the ESM the common backstop of the Single Resolution Fund of the Banking Union, is also discussed. It is argued that the ESM has only had a minor side role in the critical policy juncture presented by the pandemic, while funding the war in Ukraine might bring about a new role for the ESM.

Keywords: European Stability Mechanism, Pandemic Crisis Support Facility, Single Resolution Fund, common backstop, Article 125 TFEU, no bail-out

1. Introduction

The euro area Member States created the European Stability Mechanism (ESM) in 2012 as a reaction to the financial and debt crisis that had emerged a few years earlier.² The ESM was the result of political necessity and legal constraint, both stemming from the asymmetrical structure of the Economic and Monetary Union (EMU). Through their common currency the euro area Member States had a shared destiny, which prompted them to give financial assistance if one of them was nearing bankruptcy. Yet the EMU construction lacked a common economic policy due to which the Member States were unable to prevent each other from amassing unsustainable levels of public debt and from sharing the risks of economic crises through common fiscal capacity. In practice, the rules on economic policy coordination of Articles 121 and 126 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) and the Stability and Growth Pact (SGP)³ were not effective in preventing excessive indebtedness while the no bail-out clause of Article 125 TFEU forbids the EU and the Member States from giving financial assistance to economically distressed Member States. Through the ESM and its predecessor the European Financial Stability Facility (EFSF), the Member States were able to organize rescue packages totalling billions of euros to five default-nearing euro area Member

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² This chapter builds on Tomi Tuominen, 'Mechanisms of financial stabilisation' in Federico Fabbrini and Marco Ventoruzzo (eds), *Research Handbook on EU Economic Law* (Edward Elgar 2019).

³ Resolution of the European Council on the Stability and Growth Pact, O. J. 1997, C 236/1. See Chapter 20, 'NGEU & the new Stability & Growth Pact', by Lucio Pench.

States: EUR 6,28 billion to Cyprus (2013–2016), EUR 202,77 billion to Greece (2012–2015 and 2015–2018), EUR 17,70 billion to Ireland (2010–2013), EUR 20,00 billion to Portugal (2011–2014), and EUR 41,33 billion to Spain (2012–2013).⁴ This assistance took the form of loans, which the ESM and the EFSF financed by issuing debt instrument to the public markets that were backed up by the Member States.

The ESM is deeply interconnected with the other economic governance and financial supervision measures that the EU and the Member States took in the aftermath of the euro area financial and debt crisis,⁵ which lasted approximately from 2008 to 2015. Furthermore, being adopted in the heat of the crisis, the ESM, and the other crisis response measures as well, were compromises and thus deemed ‘incomplete’ in many respects. The Banking Union, for example, still lacks its third pillar, a common deposit guarantee system,⁶ and a common backstop for funding the resolution of failing banks that are systematically too important to be left to the mercy of traditional illiquidity procedures such as bankruptcy.⁷ It was therefore evident that the ESM, along with the other economic governance and financial supervision measures adopted at the beginning of the last decade,⁸ were to be developed in the future.

The COVID-19 crisis offered a window of opportunity to further European integration, especially in the economic domain.⁹ Indeed, the EU seems to develop through crises, and the COVID-19 pandemic was no exception in this sense. But what was the fate of the ESM in this critical policy juncture? How did the COVID-19 crisis, and more recently the war in Ukraine, which also has furthered European integration,¹⁰ affect the ESM? Has the ESM transformed in a similar manner as have many other instruments of economic governance and financial supervision? In answering these questions, this article details how the pandemic prompted one immediate response related to the ESM and gave further impetus to another, more long term and previously dormant initiative. The immediate response was that within the confines of the ESM as such a new assistance instrument, the Pandemic Crisis Support Facility (PCSF), was adopted – yet it was never used. The other effect that the pandemic had was that the amendment of the ESM Treaty, on which the Member States had already reached a provisional agreement in 2018, now gained new traction. An amendment to the ESM Treaty whereby the ESM would become the common backstop for the Banking Union, was signed in January 2021. This amendment, however, has not come into force as the Italian parliament has not ratified it. It is therefore argued, that the effects of the pandemic on economic governance and financial supervision in Europe lie elsewhere than in the ESM. However, the agreed amendments to the ESM Treaty could be ratified at a later point in time or the ESM could be brought within the EU’s own legal order. Moreover, the war in Ukraine can prompt the Member States to devise new functions for the ESM, such as using its paid-in capital to

⁴ See ‘Programme overview’

<<https://www.esm.europa.eu/financial-assistance/programme-database/programme-overview>> accessed 25 January 2024.

⁵ See e.g. Federico Fabbrini, *Economic Governance in Europe: Comparative Paradoxes and Constitutional Challenges* (Oxford University Press 2016) 2–10; Tomi Tuominen, *The Euro Crisis and Constitutional Pluralism: Financial Stability but Constitutional Inequality* (Edward Elgar 2021) 24–29.

⁶ See e.g. Christy Petit, ‘Differentiated Governance in the Banking Union: Single Mechanisms, Joint Teams, and Opting-Ins’ [2022] *European Papers - A Journal on Law and Integration* 889, 890.

⁷ See e.g. Lucia Quaglia, ‘The politics of an ‘incomplete’ Banking Union and its ‘asymmetric’ effects’ [2019] *Journal of European Integration* 955,

⁸ See Chapter 4, ‘Covid-19 & financial union’, by Christy Petit.

⁹ See e.g. Stella Ladi and Dimitris Tsarouhas, ‘EU economic governance and Covid-19: policy learning and windows of opportunity’ [2020] *Journal of European Integration* 1041.

¹⁰ See Federico Fabbrini, *EU Fiscal Capacity: Legal Integration After Covid-19 and the War in Ukraine* (Oxford University Press 2022).

give financial assistance to Ukraine and thereby circumvent the veto of non-euro area Member States, most notably Hungary.

This chapter is structured as follows. Section 2 explains the role and functioning of the ESM, as it currently stands. Then, sections 3 and 4 discuss respectively the PCSF and the (so far) failed proposal to ratify the amendment of the ESM Treaty. In both sections the process and the substance of such a change are first detailed, and then examined from a legal perspective. Analysis of the PCSF necessarily focuses on the Court of Justice's (CJEU) seminal ruling in *Pringle*,¹¹ in which the CJEU ruled on the legality of the ESM. In analysing the amendment of the ESM Treaty, focus is given to the German Federal Constitutional Court's (GFCC) ruling on its national ratification.¹² Finally, section 5 concludes and gives a short prospect of what the future might hold for the ESM.

2. The European Stability Mechanism as an institution

This section explains the legal nature of the ESM, its governance structure, the various decision-making procedures utilised by the different bodies of the ESM, its capital structure and the use of this capital. Furthermore, the various assistance instruments that the ESM has at its disposal are also discussed as is the conditionality of ESM assistance.

The euro area Member States established the ESM by an international treaty.¹³ This was preceded by an amendment of Article 136 TFEU,¹⁴ which now states that the Member States whose currency is the euro may establish a stability mechanism to be activated if indispensable to safeguard the stability of the euro area as a whole. Furthermore, the amendment also specifies that the granting of any financial assistance under the mechanism will be made subject to strict conditionality.

In the ESM Treaty, the euro area Member States are called ESM Members. After Croatia's accession to the EMU in 2023, there are now 20 ESM Members. Due to being established with an international treaty between the Member States, the ESM functions outside the scope of EU law. What is more, despite the close connection it has with the EU's regime of economic governance and financial supervision, it is not an official institution of the EU but a permanent international organisation headquartered in Luxembourg. As indicated in the preamble of the ESM Treaty, the ESM intends to safeguard the financial stability of the euro area (Preamble 6 ESM Treaty). To do so, it can offer loans and direct financial assistance to ESM Members and banks (Arts 13–18 ESM Treaty). It finances its actions by issuing debt instruments on the public markets. In order to do this, the ESM Members have given it its own capital and have committed to pay in more capital if need be.

The ESM has a three-layer governance structure. At the top sits the Board of Governors, comprising of national finance ministers (Art 5 ESM Treaty). The Board of Governors is essentially a political organ due to its composition. This is so because it decides on issues that require political legitimacy: the use of the ESM's resources, which in essence constitutes a

¹¹ C-370/12 *Pringle* ECLI:EU:C:2012:756.

¹² BVerfG, Order of the Second Senate of 13 October 2022 - 2 BvR 1111/21.

¹³ Treaty Establishing the ESM, signed on 2 February 2012,

<<https://www.esm.europa.eu/legal-documents/esm-treaty>> accessed 25 January 2024.

¹⁴ European Council Decision of 25 March 2011 amending Article 136 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union with regard to a stability mechanism for Member States whose currency is the euro [2011] OJ L91/1.

bail-out, can ultimately lead to the use of tax-payer's money, as is explained at the end of this section. The Commission and ECB may participate in the Board's meetings as observers. The Board is chaired by the President of the Eurogroup. Second, there is the Board of Directors, to which each ESM Member appoints one director, who are experts in economic and financial matters. Most directors are secretaries of state or hold similar high-ranking semi-political government offices. They are to carry out specific tasks that the Governors delegate to them or that are assigned to them by the ESM Treaty (Art 6 ESM Treaty). Third, the Managing Director is appointed by the Governors and is responsible for the day-to-day management of the ESM (Art 7 ESM Treaty).

There are four different decision-making procedures that the Board of Governors can follow: mutual agreement (unanimity), a qualified majority of either 85 or 80 per cent of the votes cast, or a simple majority. Mutual agreement is required for issues such as providing stability support from the ESM, the choice of instrument used for support, calling in authorised unpaid capital, changing the authorised capital stock and adapting the maximum lending volume (Art 5(6) ESM Treaty). The emergency voting procedure, which requires a qualified majority of 85 per cent of the votes cast, can be used to grant financial assistance when the Commission and the ECB both concluded that 'the economic and financial sustainability of the euro area' is threatened if action by the ESM is not taken. This procedure covers both the decision to give assistance and the conditions of assistance (Arts 4(4) and 5(6) (f)–(g) ESM Treaty). The main decision-making procedure of the ESM, the 'normal' qualified majority procedure, requiring a majority of 80 per cent of the votes cast, applies to several key issues relating to the functioning of the ESM: setting out by-laws of the ESM, appointing its Managing Director, approving its annual accounts, waiving the immunity of the various officials of the ESM, and resolving disputes on the interpretation of the ESM Treaty (Art 5(7) ESM Treaty).

Germany (26.74 per cent) and France (20.08 per cent) are the only ESM Members to hold a veto in both situations utilising a qualified majority, whereas Italy (17.64 per cent) only holds a veto in the emergency voting procedure mandating the higher threshold. Conversely, the lower threshold of the normal voting procedure will be reached by just the votes of the five biggest contributors; together Germany, France, Italy, Spain (11.72 per cent) and the Netherlands (5.63 per cent) possess 81.81 per cent of the votes. As all of the other ESM Members hold only a few per cent each, reaching the higher threshold of the emergency voting procedure requires that several of the smaller Members vote in favour of the proposal as well.

Both thresholds have been criticised. First, as the aim of the ESM is to safeguard the financial stability of the euro area (Preamble 6 ESM Treaty), the scope of the emergency voting procedure concerns 'the statutory aim of the ESM'.¹⁵ Meaning, that the most relevant decisions to be taken by the ESM are subject to the emergency voting procedure. Second, the fact that many relevant decisions are subject to the 80 per cent threshold results in Germany and France being the 'hegemonic parties' in the management of the ESM.¹⁶

The above described system of decision-making means, that although the ESM can be used against the will of individual ESM Members, the total amount of commitments given by a Member cannot be increased without their consent. The level of authorised capital stock can be changed by the Board of Governors, by mutual agreement, and this requires national ratification (Art 10 ESM Treaty). The capital structure of the ESM consists of paid-in capital and callable capital. As of January 2024, the total authorised capital stock is EUR 704,8

¹⁵ Fabbrini (n 4) 132.

¹⁶ Ibid.

billion, of which EUR 80,5 billion is paid-in capital and EUR 624,3 billion callable capital (Art 8 ESM Treaty). Contributions by the Members are apportioned proportionally according to their contributions to the ECB's capital, pursuant to Article 29 of the ESCB Statute (Art 11 ESM Treaty). For example, Germany's share of the ESM's capital is 26.74 per cent, which equates to EUR 189 billion, of which Germany has contributed EUR 21 billion as paid-in capital to the ESM.

The ESM may call in more authorised unpaid capital in three circumstances. The Board of Governors, deciding by mutual agreement, may make a capital call at any time (Art 9(1) ESM Treaty). Such capital calls could become relevant, for example, in the case of a financial crisis, when the credibility of the ESM to safeguard the financial stability of the euro area would need to be reinforced. Second, the Board of Directors may call in authorised unpaid capital by simple majority decision to restore the level of paid-in capital if the amount of the latter has reduced by the absorption of losses below that of EUR 80,5 billion (Art 9(2) ESM Treaty), which is the total amount of paid-in capital as indicated above. Third, the Managing Director shall call authorised unpaid capital in a timely manner if needed to avoid the ESM being in default of any scheduled or other payment obligation due to ESM creditors (Art 9(3) ESM Treaty). This procedure exists essentially for the purpose of rolling over old debt. No capital calls have been made thus far.

The ESM can activate a host of different assistance instruments. These include direct loans (either precautionary¹⁷ or actual loans, Arts 14 and 16 ESM Treaty), loans for the recapitalisation of banks (Art 15 ESM Treaty), and primary or secondary market support by acquiring the ESM Member's bonds (Arts 17 and 18 ESM Treaty). In 2014, the Board of Governors of the ESM, following the procedure prescribed in Article 19 ESM Treaty, adopted the direct bank recapitalisation instrument.¹⁸ Through this instrument, and only as last resort, the ESM can recapitalise banks directly after private investors have first been bailed-in, in accordance with the Bank Recovery and Resolution Directive (BRRD).¹⁹ It is also worth pointing out, that with the primary market support facility of Article 17 ESM Treaty, the ESM is allowed to purchase government bonds from the primary markets, directly from Member States that is – something, which the ECB is explicitly prohibited from doing under Article 123 TFEU.²⁰ As of January 2024, the ESM has so far given loans within a macroeconomic adjustment programme (Cyprus, Greece, Ireland and Portugal) and loans for indirect bank recapitalisation (Spain).²¹

The possible activation of the financial assistance instruments begins by a request for assistance by an ESM Member. The request shall indicate which assistance instrument should be used. The Commission and the ECB then assess the overall situation from the perspective of the requesting Member as well as the whole euro area. Based on this assessment, the Board of Governors may decide to grant financial assistance, after which it shall entrust the Commission to negotiate a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the requesting Member. The decision to grant assistance is taken by the Governors either by mutual

¹⁷ There are two types of precautionary credit lines: the Precautionary Conditioned Credit Line (PCCL) and the Enhanced Conditions Credit Line (ECCL). The PCCL is available to Members whose economic and financial situation is fundamentally sound, whereas the ECCL is meant for Members whose economic and financial situation remains sound but that do not comply with the eligibility criteria for PCCL.

¹⁸ See ESM, Press release, 12 August 2014, 'ESM direct bank recapitalisation instrument adopted'.

¹⁹ Directive 2014/59/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 May 2014 establishing a framework for the recovery and resolution of credit institutions and investment firms [2014] OJ L173/190

²⁰ See Chapter 3, Fiscal union, by Fabian Amtenbrink.

²¹ See 'Financial assistance instruments' <<https://www.esm.europa.eu/financial-assistance/lending-toolkit>> accessed 25 January 2024.

agreement or through qualified majority if the emergency voting procedure is used. The technicalities of the financial assistance facility are drawn up by the Managing Director and accepted by the Board of Directors (Art 13 ESM Treaty).

Conditionality of financial assistance is a key element of the ESM, as stipulated in Article 3 ESM Treaty and Article 136(3) TFEU. Assistance can only be granted through the ESM if the situation adheres to the four principles spelled out in Article 12 ESM:

If [i)] indispensable to safeguard the financial stability of the euro area as a whole and of its Member States, the ESM may provide stability support to an ESM Member [ii)] subject to strict conditionality, [iii)] appropriate to the financial assistance instrument chosen. Such [iv)] conditionality may range from a macro-economic adjustment programme to continuous respect of pre-established eligibility conditions.

The Council of the European Union is also involved through the Two-Pack legislation.²² An ESM Member requesting financial assistance has to prepare a macroeconomic adjustment programme in agreement with the Commission. This programme has to be fully consistent with the MoU that has been agreed between the Commission and the requesting Member. The specificities of conditionality are detailed in the MoU. The Council, acting by a qualified majority on a proposal from the Commission, shall approve the macroeconomic adjustment programme (MAP). Furthermore, the Commission and the ECB shall then monitor the implementation of the programme after financial assistance is granted.²³ The MAP may focus on issues ranging from the functioning of the country's financial system to labour markets, or even the judiciary.²⁴

Although the ESM is in some sense a bail-out mechanism, it tries to prioritise bail-in. This is reflected in the fact that only loans by the International Monetary Fund enjoy preferred creditor status over ESM loans (Preamble 13 ESM Treaty).²⁵ When it comes to the recapitalisation of banks, the BRRD requires a contribution to loss absorption and recapitalisation equal to an amount not less than 8 per cent of total liabilities including own funds of the institution under resolution before government financial stabilisation tools (i.e. bail-in through the ESM) can be used.²⁶ This shows the interplay of the ESM with the second resolution pillar of the Banking Union.

Why does the ESM's use require political legitimacy and how can it result in the use of tax-payers' money? Although the ESM finances its actions by emitting bonds to the public markets, the ESM's capital, which the Members contribute, will ultimately be used to repay these bonds if everything else fails. Indeed, the very purpose of the ESM's capital structure is to enable it to acquire cheap financing from the markets, which it then disburses to its Members through assistance operations. Although according to Article 25 ESM Treaty a defaulting Member remains liable to the ESM and will need to repay its share, how likely is it that they will do so in full in all circumstances? Out of the five aid-receiving Members Spain

²² See Chapter 20, 'NGEU & the new Stability & Growth Pact', by Lucio Pench.

²³ Regulation (EU) No 472/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the strengthening of economic and budgetary surveillance of Member States in the euro area experiencing or threatened with serious difficulties with respect to their financial stability [2013] OJ L40/1, Art 7.

²⁴ See e.g. Michael Ioannidis, 'EU Financial Assistance Conditionality After Two Pack' [2014] *Zeitschrift für ausländisches öffentliches Recht und Völkerrecht* 61.

²⁵ See Statement by the Eurogroup. Brussels, 28 November 2010.

²⁶ Directive 2014/59/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 May 2014 establishing a framework for the recovery and resolution of credit institutions and investment firms [2014] OJ L173/190, Arts 37(10)(a) and 56.

has so far repaid 60.24 per cent, Portugal 7.32 per cent and Greece 7.28 per cent of the loans they received, while Cyprus and Ireland have yet to repay anything.²⁷

As was explained above, in its current form the ESM has conducted six assistance operations. All of these took place about a decade ago. It therefore seems that the ESM was useful in addressing the effects of the euro area financial and debt crisis, but what has its role been during and after the COVID-19 crisis?

3. The Pandemic Crisis Support Facility

This section discusses the role of the ESM during and after the COVID-19 crisis. The timeline for adopting the Pandemic Crisis Support Facility (PCSF) within the ESM is first described, after which its content and use are discussed. The section then analyses the PCSF from a constitutional perspective, namely in light of Articles 122 and 125 TFEU.

Very soon after the severity of the COVID-19 crisis became apparent the Eurogroup issued a report on envisioned policy responses. The report, which was published on 9 April 2020, totalled almost twenty different policy responses.²⁸ One of these was the establishment of a ‘safety net’ for the euro area. It was proposed that the ESM be equipped with instruments that could be used, as needed, in a manner adapted to the nature of the symmetric shock caused by COVID-19.

In practice, a new Pandemic Crisis Support Facility (PCSF) was established to act as a safeguard for euro area Member States affected by the external shock caused by the pandemic. The European Council endorsed this proposal in its video conference a few weeks later.²⁹ The Commission took a rather lenient view on the proposed new credit facility and especially the loosened criteria (if compared to normal ESM assistance).³⁰ The Eurogroup then issued a statement on the support facility³¹ and a term sheet detailing the conditions for the use of the new facility.³² The PCSF was finally adopted by the ESM Board of Governors on 15 May 2020, and became operational.³³ The PCSF was in operation until the end of 2022. It was never used as no ESM Member applied for funding from the PCSF.

The purpose of the PCSF was to provide a credit line to the ESM Members for financing direct and indirect health, cure and prevention related costs stemming from the COVID-19 crisis, incurred since February 2020. The PCSF thus differed from traditional support from the ESM, as the former could only have been used for the narrow health related purpose while the latter can be used as part of the general budget of the country facing severe financing difficulties.³⁴ The total volume of loans that the PCSF could have provided

²⁷ ‘Programme Overview’

<<https://www.esm.europa.eu/financial-assistance/programme-database/programme-overview>> accessed 25 January 2024.

²⁸ Eurogroup, Press release, 9 April 2020, ‘Report on the comprehensive economic policy response to the COVID-19 pandemic’

²⁹ European Council, Statements and remarks, 23 April 2020, ‘Conclusions of the President of the European Council following the video conference of the members of the European Council, 23 April 2020’.

³⁰ European Commission, Letter to the President of the Eurogroup, 7 May 2020.

³¹ Eurogroup, Press release, 8 May 2020, ‘Eurogroup Statement on the Pandemic Crisis Support’.

³² ‘Term sheet: ESM Pandemic Crisis Support’, 8 May 2020.

³³ ESM, Meeting of the Board of Governors, Summary of decisions, 15 May 2020.

³⁴ See Mauro Megliani, ‘The ESM Pandemic Crisis Support Facility: A Changing Conditionality?’ [2022] *European Business Law Review* 227, 230.

amounted to EUR 240 billion. Each ESM Member could have received loans amounting to 2 per cent of their national Gross Domestic Product (at 2019 figures). The ESM would have financed these loans through its normal operating procedures, by issuing financial instruments to the markets. The eligibility criteria were crafted and interpreted so that all ESM Members fulfilled them according to the Commission's pre-assessment.³⁵

The PCSF took the form of ESM precautionary financial assistance, more specifically it would have constituted a form of Enhanced Conditions Credit Line (ECCL). The legal basis of the PCSF was Article 14 ESM Treaty and the ESM Guideline on Precautionary Financial Assistance. According to Article 14(2) ESM Treaty, the conditionality attached to the ESM precautionary financial assistance shall be detailed in the MoU, which the receiving ESM Member must sign according to Article 13(3) ESM Treaty. In the assistance programmes initiated following the euro area crisis this conditionality took the form of so-called austerity measures, for example severe cuts on public expenses and labour market reforms.³⁶ In stark contrast to this, support from the PCSF would have only required that the funds are used for the specific purpose for which the PCSF was established: for financing direct and indirect health, cure and prevention related costs stemming from the COVID-19 crisis. Monitoring would have been based on the ESM Treaty itself (Art 13(7) ESM Treaty) and the Two-Pack Regulation (EU) No 472/2013.³⁷

According to the ESM itself,³⁸ as well as one academic commentator,³⁹ its mere existence was enough to calm the markets. Whether this is true is of course difficult to assess. One would be inclined to draw a parallel between the PCSF and the ECB's Outright Monetary Transactions (OMT) programme.⁴⁰ The OMT programme was announced by the ECB in 2012, during the darkest hours of the euro area financial and debt crisis. It too was never used as its mere announcement had a positive market reaction; the ECB's proclamation that it is willing to do 'whatever it takes' was both convincing and reassuring.

However, what seems like a more convincing explanation for why the PCSF was never used is that there was ample money available to the Member States from other sources. Indeed, the NextGenerationEU (NGEU), the EU's main economic reaction to the COVID-19 crisis, had a capacity of EUR 800 billion through the Recovery and Resilience Facility.⁴¹ And the ECB's Pandemic Emergency Purchase Programme (PEPP) was even larger, with a capacity of over EUR 1000 billion. Although there was no formal conditionality requirement attached to the PCSF, ESM Members could have feared that some form of austerity would still be required from them later on.⁴² The non-use of the PCSF might thus be explained by the fact that to the ESM Members the NGEU seemed like a 'carrot' while assistance from the ESM a 'stick'.⁴³

³⁵ This assessment is no longer available online but its content is summarised in the European Parliament brief 'The ESM Pandemic Crisis Support', PE 651.350v2- August 2020.

³⁶ See Ioannidis (n 23).

³⁷ Regulation (EU) No 472/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2013 on the strengthening of economic and budgetary surveillance of Member States in the euro area experiencing or threatened with serious difficulties with respect to their financial stability [2013] OJ L 140/1.

³⁸ See statement at <<https://www.esm.europa.eu/content/europe-response-corona-crisis>> accessed 25 January 2024.

³⁹ See Francesco Martucci, 'The Solidarity Framework: Towards a New Pillar of the EMU?' in Ruth Weber (ed), *The Financial Constitution of European Integration: Follow the Money?* (Hart 2023) 153.

⁴⁰ See Chapter 2, 'Monetary Union', by Annelieke Mooij; Vestert Borger, 'Outright Monetary Transaction and the stability mandate of the ECB: *Gauweiler*' [2016] *Common Market Law Review* 139.

⁴¹ See Chapter 8, 'Recovery & Resilience Facility' by *Stefania Baroncelli*.

⁴² Martucci (n 38) 153.

⁴³ Fabbrini (n 9), section 4.3.

When analysing the PCSF from a constitutional perspective, three observations stand out. First, the EU and the Member States have utilised all the legal avenues at their disposal when crafting an economic response to the pandemic. PCSF assistance would have been similar to the type of assistance that Article 122(2) TFEU is supposed to be used for.⁴⁴ If a Member State is facing ‘difficulties or is seriously threatened with severe difficulties caused by natural disasters or exceptional occurrences beyond its control’, Article 122(2) TFEU empowers the EU to grant direct financial support to the Member State in question. The Article was first utilised in the wake of the euro area financial and debt crisis for the adoption of the European Financial Stabilisation Mechanism (EFSM),⁴⁵ which has since then been replaced by the ESM.⁴⁶ The CJEU addressed the scope of Article 122(2) TFEU as a legal basis in *Pringle*, which concerned the Member States’ capacity to adopt the ESM outside the scope of EU law. The CJEU concluded that Article 122(2) TFEU solely concerns financial assistance granted by the EU and not that granted by the Member States, and that granting financial assistance is not an exclusive competence of the EU.⁴⁷ Article 122(2) TFEU would clearly facilitate the EU giving financial assistance in a situation like the pandemic, as the Member States were faced with difficulties caused ‘by natural disasters or exceptional occurrences beyond [their] control’. Yet, as the CJEU concluded in *Pringle*, it does not preclude the Member States from creating the ESM and giving assistance through it. Legally speaking, then, the Member States could have resorted to either option during the pandemic; and indeed, they did, as Article 122 TFEU is one of the legal bases of the NGEU.⁴⁸

Second, what distinguishes the PCSF from the NGEU programme is that the latter is part of EU law whereas the former is not.⁴⁹ This observation could be read in multiple ways. An intuitive argument would be that again resorting to a measure outside the remit of EU law properly shows that the EU’s legal order is not fit for reacting to the various types of crises it is constantly faced with. This would echo the point made during the euro area financial and debt crisis,⁵⁰ when the Member States had to resort to international law on two occasions, with the ESM and the Treaty on Stability, Coordination and Governance in the Economic and Monetary Union (TSCG).⁵¹ Conversely, one could also argue that with the NGEU – which was decisive for tackling the pandemic unlike the PCSF – the EU is now adopting a totally new approach for mitigating economic crises; that the EU is trying to create its own fiscal capacity within the confines of its own legal order.⁵² While this is undoubtedly true, the EU’s

⁴⁴ See Päivi Leino-Sandberg and Matthias Ruffert, ‘Next Generation EU and its Constitutional Ramifications: A Critical Assessment’ [2022] *Common Market Law Review* 433, 436.

⁴⁵ Council Regulation (EU) No 407/2010 establishing a European financial stabilisation mechanism [2010] OJ L118/1.

⁴⁶ See Tuominen (n 1).

⁴⁷ C-370/12 *Pringle* ECLI:EU:C:2012:756, paras 118–120. See Vestert Borger, ‘The ESM and the European Court’s Predicament in *Pringle*’ [2013] *German Law Journal* 113 ; Gunnar Beck, ‘The Court of Justice, legal reasoning, and the Pringle case - law as the continuation of politics by other means’ [2014] *European Law Review* 234.

⁴⁸ See Chapter 22, ‘EU Fiscal Capacity and the Funding of the War in Ukraine’, by Federico Fabbrini; Federico Fabbrini, ‘The Legal Architecture of the Economic Responses to COVID-19: EMU beyond the Pandemic’ [2022] *Journal of Common Market Studies* 186.

⁴⁹ Leino-Sandberg and Ruffert (n 43), 454.

⁵⁰ See e.g. Jan-Herman Reestman, ‘The Fiscal Compact: Europe’s not always able to speak German: on the Dutch’ [2013] *European Constitutional Law Review* 480.

⁵¹ See Chapter 20, ‘NGEU & the new Stability & Growth Pact’, by Lucio Pench.

⁵² See e.g. Federico Fabbrini, ‘Next Generation Eu: Legal Structure and Constitutional Consequences’ [2020] *Cambridge Yearbook of European Legal Studies* 45.

competence to adopt the NGEU has been convincingly criticized,⁵³ which suggests that the EU's competence allocation should still be developed.

Third, the fact that there is no conditionality requirement attached to PCSF loans leads one to ask, is the PCSF in breach of the no bail-out clause of Article 125 TFEU and the ESM Treaty itself.⁵⁴ Perhaps the most difficult question the CJEU was faced with in *Pringle* was whether the ESM breaches the no bail-out clause.⁵⁵ On a literal reading, Article 125 TFEU does not prohibit the EU or the Member States from giving financial assistance to a Member State and Article 122(2) TFEU actually makes assistance possible.⁵⁶ Then, on a teleological reading, the CJEU concluded that Article 125 TFEU only prohibits unconditional assistance that leads to the receiving Member State to stray away from sound budgetary policy. The ESM respects this criterion, according to the CJEU, specifically because strict conditionality is attached to the loans granted through it, and that the aid receiving Member States remain responsible to their creditors.⁵⁷ From this perspective, the PCSF seemed to contravene Article 125 TFEU as there was no clear and strict conditionality requirement. Indeed, the very point of the PCSF was to give financial assistance to all ESM Members, which leads one to doubt whether there really is any element of conditionality involved in it.

Moreover, the question whether the PCSF would breach the no bail-out clause of Article 125 TFEU is closely linked with the issue of moral hazard.⁵⁸ Simply put, creating an assistance mechanism such as the ESM can result in profligate spending since indebted states can assume that they will receive assistance from the created mechanism if they are about to default on their creditors. The asymmetrical structure of the EMU further increases moral hazard: on the one hand, Member States are unable to curtail profligate spending by others since economic policy is a national concern, while on the other hand the common currency binds the Member States together and creates an incentive to bail-out. The purpose of Article 125 TFEU is to prevent moral hazard, and therefore the CJEU emphasized the strict conditionality requirement for ESM support in its judgement in *Pringle*.

As the pandemic caused a symmetric shock in the economies of the euro area Member States – as opposed to the asymmetric shock of the financial crisis – one would be inclined to say that the use of the PCSF would not incur moral hazard concerns in the same manner as the ESM perhaps initially did. As all ESM Members were affected by the pandemic and thus all were to have access to PCSF assistance, there was no concern for moral hazard as everyone was in the same position. Simply put, the need for assistance was not caused by the ‘bad’ economic policies of individual ESM Members, but by the sudden rise in public expenditure caused by the pandemic. Conversely, one could also argue that the very fact that PCSF assistance did not contain a similar element of conditionality than prior ESM assistance operations just increases moral hazard.

In conclusion, the adoption of the PCSF shows that the Member States were willing and able to utilize all possible means in their efforts to tackle the economic effects of the pandemic. It is difficult to say whether the adoption of the PCSF was in vain, as it was never used, or

⁵³ See Leino-Sandberg and Ruffert (n 43). According to the authors the NGEU is a nearly unconditional redistributive mechanism but there is no clear legal basis for such redistribution of wealth in the EU Treaties. In a community based on the rule of law, a mere agreement between the Heads of State or Government of the Member States should not be enough to circumvent the competence allocation of the current Treaties.

⁵⁴ Megliani (n 33), 236–240.

⁵⁵ See Tuominen (n 1) 97–98; Borger (n 46), 129–137 ; Beck (n 46) 21–34.

⁵⁶ C-370/12 *Pringle* ECLI:EU:C:2012:756, paras 130–132.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*, paras 135–145.

⁵⁸ See Kaarlo Tuori and Klaus Tuori, *The Eurozone Crisis: A Constitutional Analysis* (Cambridge University Press 2014), 126–167.

whether its mere announcement did the job, by calming the markets. While the PCSF raised interesting points with regard to Articles 122 and 125 TFEU, as a legal measure it was not as controversial as some of the other measures adopted following the pandemic. More relevant than the PCSF is the planned amendment of the ESM Treaty, through which the ESM could become the common backstop of the Banking Union, to which this chapter turns to next.

4. Reform of the ESM Treaty and the Common Backstop Function

This section discusses the so far failed efforts to amend the ESM Treaty, most notably to include into the ESM's functions to act as a common backstop to the Single Resolution Fund (SRF) of the Banking Union's resolution pillar. The common backstop function would replace the direct bank recapitalisation instrument, discussed above.⁵⁹ The process of trying to amend the ESM Treaty as well as the content of the planned amendment is first described, after which its functioning in terms of efficiency of decision-making is discussed. Lastly, the legality of the amendment is analysed through the German Federal Constitutional Court's ruling on its national ratification, especially in terms of Article 125 TFEU.

The ESM has been the object of almost constant reform proposals since its inception.⁶⁰ The first attempt was to transform the ESM into something akin to a European Monetary Fund. This would have taken place by adopting a regulation with which the ESM would have been brought within the EU's own legal order, so that its position would have corresponded to that of an EU agency.⁶¹ This legislative proposal has not progressed.⁶²

A second major effort was to amend the ESM Treaty itself. The Eurogroup agreed on this revision in its meeting on 13 June 2019.⁶³ The COVID-19 pandemic provided a window of opportunity for the much-needed reform and on 30 November 2020 the Eurogroup agreed to proceed with the agreed revision.⁶⁴ On 27 January and 8 February 2021 ESM Members signed the Agreement Amending the ESM Treaty.⁶⁵

As this was an amendment to an international treaty, all ESM Members needed to ratify it according to their national constitutional procedures. The ratification process begun in 2021. A major hurdle was cleared from the way of the amendment in October 2022, when the GFCC declared inadmissible the constitutional complaints raised against the amendment.⁶⁶

⁵⁹ See Section 2.

⁶⁰ See Mauro Megliani, 'From the European Stability Mechanism to the European Monetary Fund: There and back again' [2020] *German Law Journal* 674; Menelaos Markakis, 'The Reform of the European Stability Mechanism: Process, Substance, and the Pandemic' [2020] *Legal Issues of Economic Integration* 359.

⁶¹ See COM (2017) 827: Proposal for a COUNCIL REGULATION on the establishment of the European Monetary Fund.

⁶² See Andreu Olesti-Rayó, 'The amendment of the European Stability Mechanism' [2022] *Review of International & European Economic Law* 84, 93–96; Giovanni Zaccaroni, 'The Reform of the ESM Within a Hybrid EMU Law' [2022] *European Public Law* 373, 386–387.

⁶³ Eurogroup, Press release, 15 June 2019, 'Economic and Monetary Union: Eurogroup agrees term sheet on euro-area budgetary instrument and revised ESM treaty'.

⁶⁴ Eurogroup, Press release, 30 November 2020, 'Statement of the Eurogroup in inclusive format on the ESM reform and the early introduction of the backstop to the Single Resolution Fund'.

⁶⁵ Agreement amending the Treaty Establishing the ESM, signed on 27 January and 8 February 2021, <<https://www.esm.europa.eu/about-esm/esm-reform-documents/esm-treaty-amending-agreement>> accessed 25 January 2024.

⁶⁶ BVerfG, Order of the Second Senate of 13 October 2022 - 2 BvR 1111/21.

All other ESM Members except Italy ratified the amendments rather quickly.⁶⁷ In exchange for ratification Italy tried to negotiate more flexibility into the budgetary rules of the SGP.⁶⁸ In December 2023, the Italian Parliament finally voted against the amendment.⁶⁹ Whether Italy decides to ratify it later remains to be seen.

The content of the amendments are threefold. First, the ESM's role would be enhanced by giving it a stronger role in the design, negotiation and monitoring of conditionality in future financial assistance programmes. Second, the instruments that are at the ESM's disposal would also be further developed, most notably by replacing the direct bank recapitalisation instrument by the common backstop. Third, and related to the previous point, the ESM would become the common backstop to the SRF. Through the common backstop function the ESM could lend the SRF the funds necessary for bank resolution in case the SRF's own funds would be depleted. The capacity of the common backstop would be EUR 68 billion. Repayment of these assets to the ESM would be financed in the same manners as the SRF operates normally: through contributions from the European banks directly supervised by the ECB in the Banking Union.

The content of the backstop facility is detailed in the proposed new Article 18a ESM Treaty. Support from the ESM to the SRF would cover all possible uses of the SRF. To this end, the ESM would provide a revolving credit line to the SRF. The Board of Governors defines the key financial terms and conditions of the facility, whereas the Board of Directors decides whether the SRB's request for a loan is accepted. The Board of Directors takes this decision by mutual agreement (i.e. unanimity). The Board of Directors can also utilise the emergency voting procedure, whereby a decision on the use of the backstop can be made on the basis of a qualified majority, if the Commission and the ECB have concluded that the financial stability of the euro area is threatened.

The efficiency of the envisioned common backstop function has been criticised due to its decision-making procedure. Within the normal decision-making procedure, all ESM Members hold a veto, and in case of a threat to the economic and financial stability of the euro area, France, Germany and Italy each hold an individual veto as each of them holds over 15 per cent of the votes. In other words, idiosyncratic national preferences could trump supranationally agreed resolution schemes.⁷⁰ While from the perspective of efficiency this is surely true, from a democratic perspective the unanimity requirement is warranted, as the Member States are ultimately liable for the commitments of the ESM in case of default by an aid receiving Member, or in the event that the SRF cannot repay all of the loans given through the backstop facility, as discussed above.

In its decision of 13 October 2022, the GFCC analysed four issues relating to the proposed amendment.⁷¹ First, when it came to the possibility to utilise the emergency voting procedure of Article 4(4) ESM Treaty for the use of the common backstop facility, the GFCC saw this as merely an administrative matter. As the emergency voting procedure was already in

⁶⁷ See ratification table for ESM Treaty amendment, <<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/documents-publications/treaties-agreements/agreement/?id=2019035&DoCLanguage=en>> accessed 25 January 2024.

⁶⁸ See Angelo Amante and Giuseppe Fonte, 'Italy could veto deal on EU stability pact rules – Meloni' *Reuters* (13 December 2023); Giampaolo Galli, 'The reform of the ESM and why it is so controversial in Italy' [2020] *Capital Markets Law Journal* 262.

⁶⁹ Federica Pascale, 'Rome rejects European Stability Mechanism, irritates Brussels' *EURACTIV.it* (22 December 2023).

⁷⁰ See Tobias H. Tröger and Anastasia Kotovskaia, 'National Interests and Supranational Resolution in the European Banking Union' [2023] *European Business Law Review* 781, 807–808

⁷¹ BVerfG, Order of the Second Senate of 13 October 2022 - 2 BvR 1111/21.

existence, and the GFCC had previously declared the ESM as such constitutional, the GFCC saw no objections to extending the emergency voting procedure to the new powers of the ESM.⁷²

Second, the establishment of the common backstop function was not problematic either, since by doing this the direct bank recapitalisation instrument would simultaneously be removed from the ESM's toolkit.⁷³ With the direct bank recapitalisation instrument the ESM can directly support banks in distress, while through the common backstop assistance would be given to the SRF, which is managed by the SRB, an EU agency. The constitutionality of the direct bank recapitalisation instrument had been questioned under German constitutional law, since direct bank recapitalisation occurs between the ESM and a private entity, and such intrusions by public power into the sphere of private law require separate democratic legitimisation according to Article 20 of the German Constitution. The same problem does not arise in the context of the backstop facility, as assistance is not given directly to private banks but to the SRB. After this, 'the ESM will (once again) merely be "an international financial institution based on international law"'.⁷⁴

Third, the conferral of new functions to the Commission and the ECB was not problematic since these new 'powers' actually aimed at making sure that the operation of the ESM abides by EU law.⁷⁵

Lastly, the GFCC also considered whether the introduction of the common backstop function changes the no bail-out principle enshrined in Article 125 TFEU. The GFCC opined, that with the common backstop function the ESM actually gives assistance to an EU agency (the SRB) and not a Member State, which 'eases pressure on national public budgets in an indirect manner' and thereby the 'principle of national budget autonomy is not affected'.⁷⁶

The common backstop function would be a welcome addition into the ESM's toolkit of assistance instruments. It would also be crucial for finalising the Banking Union. Legally speaking, there seem to be no objections for the ratification of the agreed amendment of the ESM Treaty, neither under EU law or national constitutional law. What is withholding the process is political bargaining. Time will tell whether the non-ratification of the amendments will result in the ESM becoming obsolete as an economic governance instrument.

5. Conclusion

COVID-19 provided a window of opportunity to further European integration and to develop the EU's instruments of economic governance and financial supervision. While the various initiatives taken as a response to the pandemic undoubtedly try to fix the asymmetrical structure of the EMU and take European integration to the direction of fiscal federalism,⁷⁷ the ESM has had only a minor side role in this play: the ESM was not used during the crisis and the crisis has not resulted in the further development of the ESM. It seems, then, that more significant changes have taken place within the EU's own legal order as opposed to outside of

⁷² Ibid., para 107.

⁷³ Ibid., paras 108–112.

⁷⁴ Ibid., para 112.

⁷⁵ Ibid., paras 113–118.

⁷⁶ Ibid., paras 119–133.

⁷⁷ Federico Fabbrini, 'The Legal Architecture of the Economic Responses to COVID-19: EMU beyond the Pandemic' [2022] *Journal of Common Market Studies* 186, 197.

it, where the ESM still is situated. One would be tempted to conclude from this, that the EU's political system is starting to show signs of maturity as the most crucial developments have taken place within EU law proper.

What does the future role of the ESM look like? All of the assistance programmes conducted by the ESM have ended already almost ten years ago (although repayment of given assistance will continue long into the future). Should we thus conclude that the ESM has become redundant, either because the amended SGP is so effective that financial assistance is not necessary, or because there are now other EU instruments available for default-nearing Member States? At least there has been no demand for the type of assistance given by the ESM, presumably because assistance on better terms has been available through the NGEU.

The most likely scenario for making the ESM a relevant economic policy instrument would be that the common backstop function be included into it somehow. This could take place either by ratifying the already agreed changes to the ESM Treaty or by adopting an EU regulation with which the ESM would be re-created as an EU agency. An alternative scenario for the future of the ESM is that it would be used to finance the war in Ukraine. Debates on funding the war in Ukraine have usually focused on the European Peace Facility and the Macro-Financial Assistance Instrument.⁷⁸ It has also been proposed that the ESM's own capital be used to finance assistance to Ukraine. Indeed, Olli Rehn, who was European Commissioner for Economic and Monetary Affairs and the Euro from 2010 to 2014, and one of the architects of the response to the euro area financial and debt crisis,⁷⁹ has proposed that the ESM's capital be used to fund the war in Ukraine. Rehn's argument is, that by utilising the ESM's paid-in capital euro area Member States can avoid Hungary's veto, which it holds if decisions are taken within EU law and therefore amongst all 27 Member States.⁸⁰ Rehn is currently serving as the Governor of the Bank of Finland and in this role also a member of the Governing Council of the ECB. Whether this idea gains enough traction remains to be seen.

⁷⁸ See Federico Fabbrini, 'Funding the War in Ukraine: The European Peace Facility, the Macro-Financial Assistance Instrument, and the Slow Rise of an EU Fiscal Capacity' [2023] *Politics and Governance* 52; Chapter 22, 'TITLE', by X X.

⁷⁹ See his memoirs from those years, Olli Rehn, *Walking the Highwire: Rebalancing the European Economy in Crisis* (Palgrave Macmillan 2020).

⁸⁰ Olli Rehn, 'Europe needs a realistic and sturdy long-term strategy to support Ukraine' *STT Info* (21 December 2023).